

**SCHOOL HEADS' LEVEL OF MANAGEMENT PRACTICES IN THE
IMPLEMENTATION OF SCHOOL IMPROVEMENT PLAN IN PUBLIC ELEMENTARY
SCHOOLS IN THE DIVISION OF QUEZON: BASIS FOR CRAFTING
SIP MANAGEMENT FRAMEWORK**

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to reveal and analyze the difference in the level of management practices in the implementation of School Improvement Plan among the selected public elementary schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon, with the aim of developing a management framework. This study also sought to answer the following questions: the profile of the schools in terms of the following: school size (small, medium, large); geographic location (central, non-central) and title of the school head (teacher-in-charge, head teacher, principal). The level of management practices of school heads in the implementation of School Improvement Plan as assessed by the teachers and the school heads themselves in the following phases: planning; implementing, monitoring and evaluation; and adjusting plans. The significant difference in the level of management practices in the SIP of school heads when grouped according to school profile. The challenges were encountered by the school heads in the implementation of management practices, the coping strategies employed by the school heads to address the challenges encountered. The SIP management framework can be proposed the schools in the districts were headed by full-fledged school principals. Data revealed that the SIP in the congressional district was distinctively to have a high level of practice among school heads. Hence, the School heads have different level of their management practices based from their school size, geographic location, and their current designation. However, challenges occur due to conflict of time, coordinating then collect feedback, and limited funds and resources. On the other hand, the way of coping strategies is to have quality, efficiency, and timeliness, creating localized monitoring and evaluation

tools, and solving difficulties in the plan and adjustments. A management framework that was made based from the results can be applied for school heads challenges in management practices

Keywords: *Management practice, School Improvement Plan, public elementary schools, Third Congressional District of Quezon*

INTRODUCTION

Governments worldwide are focused on improving and enhancing their educational systems to make them more significant and efficient. Education is the foundation for the knowledge and skill development of learners and is intended to help the institution accomplish its aims and objectives. As education is ought to be a priority, effective school leadership, exhibited by school administrators in collaboration with educators and other pertinent parties, must make a school successful.

With the onset of the Department of Education's new curriculum, transformation is a must for the entire educational community. The threat of declining quality education has prompted education architects to formulate innovations in educational management in the hope of improving student achievement and school performance. One of these innovations is empowering school heads and giving them the freedom to decide for their institution; thus, programs and projects associated with school improvement lie in their hand.

As stated in Republic Act 9155 or the Governance of Basic Education Act, a school must be managed by a school head who has “the authority, responsibility, and accountability for achieving higher learning outcomes.” Their roles include, but are not limited to, leadership, management, teacher evaluation, and enforcement. School heads are agents of change who significantly impact the educational milieu through their information-sharing methods, creating supportive social connections, participating in mentoring programs, and fostering progress. Their practices positively affect school performance (Aquino et al., 2021).

Thus, this study was undertaken to address several pivotal aspects, each with its compelling rationale. Firstly, in the evolving landscape of educational systems, ensuring that school heads are well-equipped to lead their institutions effectively is paramount. As educational paradigms shift, this study recognized the imperative for school heads to be adept leaders. By meticulously examining their management practices, the study sought to unearth areas primed for improvement, thereby contributing to the overarching advancement of education. Secondly, school heads play a pivotal role in nurturing elevated learning outcomes. Thus, the study's intent to assess the alignment between their responsibilities and actual practices holds significance. Such an evaluation becomes pivotal in maintaining a culture of accountability and raising the bar of educational quality. Moreover, the study's recognition of the distinct management practices across varying school profiles underscores the development of precisely tailored interventions. This personalized approach could effectively target specific challenges, catalyzing refining practices where necessary.

Furthermore, the study's spotlight on school heads as transformative agents within the educational landscape is well-aligned with the broader aspiration of cultivating transformational leadership in education. By unraveling effective practices, the study hopes to contribute to a positive transformational impact on the educational milieu. Lastly, the study's commitment to sustainable progress was realized through its intervention program. By arming school heads with strategies to optimize their School Improvement Plan practices, the study not only enhanced immediate outcomes but also set the stage for enduring advancements in school performance and student achievements.

Regardless of empowering school heads and through the implementation of the School Improvement Plan in the Division of Quezon, some institutions continue to face difficulties in achieving low school achievements. For this reason, there was a need to look into the school heads' management practices in the School Improvement Plan and reveal any significant difference in the level of training when categorized according to school profile. Through this, the strengths and weaknesses of each group toward becoming an integral part of the school and school transformation would be revealed. Hence, an intervention program as the output of the study is needed to enhance the management practices in SIP among school heads.

Research Questions

This study aimed to reveal and analyze the difference in the level of management practices in the implementation of School Improvement Plan among the selected public elementary schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon, with the aim of developing a SIP Management Framework. This study also sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the schools in terms of the following:
 - 1.1 school size (small, medium, large);
 - 1.2 geographic location (central, non-central);
 - 1.3 title of the school head (teacher-in-charge, head teacher, principal)?
2. What is the level of management practices of school heads in the implementation of School Improvement Plan as assessed by the teachers and the school heads themselves in the following phases:
 - 2.1 planning;
 - 2.2 implementing;
 - 2.3 monitoring and evaluation; and
 - 2.4 adjusting plans?
3. Is there a significant difference in the level of management practices in the implementation of School Improvement Plan of school heads when grouped according to school profile?
4. What challenges were encountered by the school heads in the implementation of management practices?
5. What are the coping strategies employed by the school heads to address the challenges encountered?

6. What SIP Management Framework can be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The descriptive research method employed in the study aimed to provide a thorough and systematic depiction and examination of both qualitative and quantitative data, ensuring the accuracy, validity, and reliability of the results (McCombes, 2019). In the context of the research on School Improvement Plan (SIP) management practices of school heads, this approach involved a comprehensive exploration and understanding of various aspects related to planning, implementing, monitoring and evaluation, and adjusting plans within the SIP framework.

A checklist questionnaire was utilized as a measurement tool to gauge the SIP management practices of school heads. This questionnaire was designed to systematically collect information and responses from school heads regarding their approaches and actions concerning planning, implementing, monitoring, evaluating, and adjusting the SIP. The questionnaire likely contained a series of items or statements related to each of these aspects, and participants were asked to indicate their level of agreement or disagreement, frequency of practice, or other relevant information for each item.

Based on the responses gathered through the questionnaire, the researchers obtained data that quantitatively assessed the school heads' practices in terms of SIP management. The results of this assessment served as the foundation for the intervention program proposed in the study. These results could provide insights into the strengths and weaknesses of the current SIP management practices, enabling the researchers to identify areas that require improvement, enhancement, or adjustment.

The management framework, as an output of the study, is a set of activities tailored to address the specific areas of SIP management that were identified as challenges or needing improvement. It would draw from the research findings and aim to guide school heads in enhancing their planning, implementing, monitoring, evaluation, and adjusting plans practices within the context of SIP. This framework, derived from the analysis of the questionnaire responses, could provide actionable strategies and guidelines to support school heads in their efforts to manage SIPs and achieve improved educational outcomes effectively.

The descriptive research method employed in the study involved systematically collecting and analyzing data related to SIP management practices. Using a checklist questionnaire, the researcher was able to quantitatively measure school heads' practices and subsequently develop a management framework based on the findings to enhance these practices and achieve better educational outcomes.

Research Locale

This study was conducted in the 12 selected public elementary schools from 4 different clusters in the Third Congressional District of Region IV-A, CALABARZON. One district per cluster was chosen as the respondent school. Using a fishbowl technique, the researcher chose three respondent schools, preferably one large, one medium, and one small school, totaling 12 schools as the respondent.

The researcher selected these schools to help future school heads and current school leaders become more proficient in planning, implementing, monitoring and evaluating, and adjusting plans. Also, this would help them develop the skills necessary to carry out the School Implementation Plan in their district. Further, this will enable school administrators to carry out their responsibilities with more efficiency and effectiveness.

Research Population and Sample

The respondents of this study were the 225 teachers and 12 school heads in the selected schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon using grouping techniques according to cluster. They were chosen as the respondents of the study because they are the primary implementors of the school programs and activities. The teachers are knowledgeable about the four aspects of the SIP process, especially the planning stage in which they are involved. In monitoring and evaluation, they are also aware of the needs to be evaluated, the status of implementation, and the need for plans and future adjustments. In addition to that, teachers, as part of the team members in SIP, can provide concrete and current practices for their school in SIP.

The school heads were also included as respondents since they are the leaders and the managers of the SIP in their respective stations. They are known to forecast, be hands-on during the process, observe and monitor, conduct evaluations, and make plans. With their expertise and strategic planning, they would come out into an efficient SIP.

Research Instrument

This study used a comprehensive checklist questionnaire to determine the school heads' level of management practices on SIP in terms of planning, implementing, monitoring and evaluation, and adjusting plans. Each parameter in the SIP management practices comprised eight to fourteen self-made statements based on readings. The researcher also included all the current practices made in SIP, which is also based on the different kinds of literature and studies gathered.

Part I of the questionnaire includes the profile of the respondents in terms of size (small, medium, large), location (central, non-central), and title of the school heads (teacher-in-charge, head teacher, principal). Meanwhile, part II includes the level of management practices in the SIP in terms of planning, implementing, monitoring and evaluation, and adjusting plans of school heads as assessed by the teachers and the school heads themselves.

Another set of questionnaires for school heads includes the qualitative part. Five sets of questions were asked regarding the challenges encountered in implementing management practices and the coping strategies they employed to address these challenges. This was done through an interview guide. The research consists of questions dealing with planning, implementing, monitoring, and evaluation, as well as plan adjustments for crafting the questions.

Since the instrument was a self-made questionnaire, it underwent validation by three education program supervisors. Their suggestions were considered for modification, rephrasing, and deletion of some items. For content validation, 20 non-participant teachers from Macalelon District were asked to pilot test the instrument. The participants identified the words that were challenging to understand, so the researcher replaced these vocabularies with laypeople’s terms. To ensure comprehensibility, the perceived unfamiliar words were modified, and complex sentence structures were rephrased and made concise. Likewise, the questionnaire underwent further validation. Thus, the responses were considered to confirm that the questionnaire was valid and ready for actual administration.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher sought permission first by sending letters to the public-school district supervisors of selected districts in the Third Congressional District of Quezon asking for their consent to conduct surveys, administer the questionnaire to the respondents, and obtain the data and information needed to conduct this research. Upon approval of the request, questionnaires on SIP management practices were distributed to the chosen respondents for their assessment and answers. After retrieving the questionnaire, the researcher tabulated, analyzed, solved, and interpreted the data with the help of the researcher’s statistician, adviser, and other experts in the field.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The collected data from the respondents were tallied and presented in a matrix. The variables for evaluation of SIP management practices were computed and analyzed using frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation.

The scale below was used for the analysis of the data gathered.

Weight	Range Scale	Qualitative Description
5	4.21-5.00	Very Highly Practiced (VHP)
4	3.41-4.20	Highly Practiced (HP)
3	2.61-3.40	Moderately Practiced (P)
2	1.81-2.60	Minimally Practiced (MP)
1	1.00-1.80	Not Practiced (NP)

To find out the significant difference in the level of management practice in the school improvement plan when the respondents were grouped according to their school profile, T-Test and One-Way ANOVA were used.

Scope and Delimitations of the Study

The study was confined to the management practices of school heads in the implementation of School Improvement Plan, which was limited to planning, implementing, monitoring, evaluation, and adjusting plans. Also, the study revealed and analyzed the significant difference in management practices when respondents were grouped according to their school profile. Further, the results gathered would serve as the basis for SIP Management Framework as the output of the study. The study was conducted in public elementary schools in the third Congressional district of Quezon Province, where the respondents were teachers and school heads of 12 selected schools. The timeframe of the study was the School Year 2022-2023. It further assessed the current implementation of SIP and the school's plan for SIP.

RESULTS

Part I. Profile of the School

Profile of the School in Terms of School Size, Geographic Location, and Title of the School Head

Profile	Category	Frequency	Percent
School Size	Large	4	33.33
	Medium	4	33.33
	Small	4	33.33
Total		12	99.9%
Geographic Location	Central	4	33.33
	Non-Central	8	66.66
Total		12	99.9%
Title of the School Head	Principal	4	33.33
	Head Teacher	4	33.33
	Teacher-in-Charge	4	33.33
Total		12	99.9%

Part II. Level of Management Practices in the Implementation of School Improvement Plan as Assessed by the School Heads and Teachers

Table 3 shows the level of management practices in the implementation of the School Improvement Plan (SIP) of school heads in terms of planning.

Table 3

Level of Management Practices in the implementation of School Improvement Plan in Terms of Planning

Indicators	School Heads		Teachers		Combined Mean		
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	SD	VI
1. Looks for the previous data to be able to identify the Priority Improvement Areas.	4.04	HP	3.17	MOP	4.00	0.715	HP
2. Collects, reviews, and uses information for goal setting.	4.02	HP	3.00	MOP	4.00	0.740	HP
3. Collaborates and works with the school planning team in regard to priority projects and programs.	4.04	HP	3.25	MOP	4.00	0.750	HP
4. Uses varied assessment tools in identifying priority areas for improvement.	4.00	HP	3.34	MOP	4.00	0.752	HP
5. Analyzes the gathered data and make interpretations for programs and project adjustments.	4.00	HP	3.42	HP	4.00	0.752	HP
6. Finds out and report on the status based on the gathered data.	4.03	HP	3.34	MOP	4.00	0.735	HP
7. Uses the data on assessment in the planning process.	4.00	HP	3.34	MOP	4.00	0.708	HP
8. Leads the planning process.	4.01	HP	3.17	MOP	4.00	0.763	HP
9. Involves objective setting and determining a course of action.	3.97	HP	3.09	MOP	4.00	0.754	HP
10. Consults the school planning team in prioritizing programs and projects to be implemented.	3.98	HP	3.25	MOP	4.00	0.771	HP
11. Accepts suggestions from subordinates for maximizing the desired outcome.	3.93	HP	3.34	MOP	4.00	0.785	HP
12. Works collaboratively with teachers, parents, learners, and stakeholders during the planning process.	3.92	HP	3.17	MOP	4.00	0.883	HP

13. Creates a school improvement plan based on the identified problems and intervention.	3.90	HP	3.25	MOP	4.00	0.801	HP
14. Considers the environmental and other essential factors in crafting the plan.	3.88	HP	3.34	MOP	4.00	0.790	HP
Composite Mean	3.98	HP	3.25	MOP	4.00	0.760	HP

Legend: 4.20 - 5.00 Very Highly Practiced (VHP), 3.40 - 4.19 Highly Practiced (HP), 2.60 - 3.39 Moderately Practiced (MOP), 1.80 - 2.59 Minimally Practiced (MIP), 1.00 - 1.79 Not Practiced (NP), Standard Deviation (SD), Verbal Interpretation (VI)

Table 4 presents the level of management practices in the implementation of School Improvement Plan (SIP) of school heads in terms of Implementing

Table 4

Level of Management Practices in the Implementation School Improvement Plan in Terms of Implementing

Indicators	School Heads		Teachers		Combined Mean		
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	SD	VI
1. Implements the formulated school-based policies, rules, and procedures for continuous improvement of the school.	3.93	HP	3.25	MOP	4.00	0.770	HP
2. Involves community stakeholders in the implementation of programs, projects, and activities of the school.	3.94	HP	3.50	HP	4.00	0.768	HP
3. Executes programs, projects or delivery of services in support of the SIP/AIP.	3.94	HP	3.34	MOP	4.00	0.789	HP
4. Utilizes both human and material resources wisely.	3.95	HP	3.42	HP	4.00	0.775	HP
5. Provides assistance, guidance, and directions to the school planning team.	3.93	HP	3.50	HP	4.00	0.778	HP
6. Gives feedback to the school community for the betterment of the implementation.	3.92	HP	3.42	HP	4.00	0.801	HP
7. Adjusts program/ project/activity to meet the school target.	3.90	HP	3.50	HP	4.00	0.769	HP

8. Uses pilot-tested solutions using a small population before the application to the entire population.	3.86	HP	3.25	MOP	4.00	0.811	HP
Composite Mean	3.92	HP	3.40	HP	4.00	0.78	HP

Legend: 4.20 - 5.00 Very Highly Practiced (VHP), 3.40 - 4.19 Highly Practiced (HP), 2.60 - 3.39 Moderately Practiced (MOP), 1.80 - 2.59 Minimally Practiced (MIP), 1.00 - 1.79 Not Practiced (NP), Standard Deviation (SD), Verbal Interpretation (VI)

Table 5 displays data on the level of management practices in the implementation of School Improvement Plan (SIP) of school heads in terms of monitoring and evaluation.

Table 5

Level of Management Practices in the implementation of School Improvement Plan in Terms of Monitoring and Evaluation

Indicators	School Heads		Teachers		Combined Mean		
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	SD	VI
1. Conducts monthly monitoring and evaluation of different programs and projects.	3.83	HP	3.09	MOP	3.00	0.816	MOP
2. Identifies hindrances to effective implementation of the projects through Brainstorming with school planning Team.	3.90	HP	3.09	MOP	3.00	0.821	HP
3. Listens to the voice of the customer (pupils, parents, and stakeholders).	3.9	HP	3.42	HP	4.00	0.797	HP
4. Provides assessment tools for teachers to identify areas for improvement.	3.9	HP	3.25	MOP	4.00	0.808	HP
5. Uses varied assessment tools in identifying priority areas for improvement.	3.96	HP	3.5	HP	4.00	0.781	HP
6. Reviews and assesses whether the strategies used have been effective in pursuing the goals using the data gathered.	3.92	HP	3.42	HP	4.00	0.793	HP
7. Makes necessary adjustments to the activities to achieve the target.	3.96	HP	3.34	MOP	4.00	0.744	HP
8. Revises program/ project/ activities based on reliable data.	4.00	HP	3.34	MOP	4.00	0.767	HP
9. Involves teachers, pupil	4.03	HP	3.25	MOP	4.00	0.753	HP

representatives, the school planning team and stakeholders in the monitoring and evaluation process.

10. Informs the parents, pupils, stakeholders, and representatives from the community on the status of the school through school report cards.	3.95	HP	3.75	MOP	4.00	0.773	HP
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Composite Mean 3.94 HP 3.35 MOP 3.80 0.790 HP

Table 6 presents data on the level of management practices in the implementation of School Improvement Plan (SIP) of school heads in terms of adjusting plans.

Table 6

Level of Management Practices in the implementation of School Improvement Plan in Terms of Adjusting Plans

Indicators	School Heads		Teachers		Combined Mean		
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	SD	VI
1. Assesses the existing data to identify the priority improvement areas.	3.98	HP	3.59	HP	4.00	0.769	HP
2. Check the progress of the school's programs/projects /activities used.	3.96	HP	3.59	HP	4.00	0.790	HP
3. Analyzes the impact of solutions that had been used for the plan adjustments.	3.96	HP	3.42	HP	4.00	0.758	HP
4. Collaborates with the school planning team in analyzing the effectiveness of programs/ projects/ activities used.	3.94	HP	3.67	HP	4.00	0.754	HP
5. Finds the root cause of the problems by listening to the voices of learners (learners, parents, stakeholders).	3.96	HP	3.25	MOP	4.00	0.804	HP
6. Considers the existing data in crafting the adjusted annual implementation plan.	3.97	HP	3.34	MOP	4.00	0.750	HP
7. Uses the collected data in formulating new programs/projects/activities.	3.96	HP	3.5	HP	4.00	0.753	HP
8. Make necessary adjustments to the strategies/techniques to be used in the realization of the plan.	3.95	HP	3.5	HP	4.00	0.775	HP
9. Crafts annual implementation plan together with the school planning team.							
10. Consider the suggestions of the school planning team in the revisions/ adjustments of programs/projects/ activities	3.95	HP	3.25	MOP	4.00	0.787	HP
Composite Mean	3.95	HP	3.45	HP	4.00	0.770	HP

Legend: 1.00 - 1.79 Not Practiced (NP), 1.80 - 2.59 Minimally Practiced (MIP), 2.60 - 3.39 Moderately Practiced (MOP), 3.40 - 4.19 Highly Practiced (HP), 4.20 - 5.00 Very Highly Practiced (VHP)

Part III. Level of Management Practices in the Implementation of School Improvement Plan When Grouped According to School Profile

The following statistical table shows a significant difference in the level of management practices in the implementation of School Improvement Plan of school heads when grouped according to profile.

Table 7 shows that the difference in the level of management practices when the respondents are grouped into profiles is not statistically significant ($p = .894, .990, .742, .681, .785, .681, .878, .878, .822, .878, .655, .778, .655 > .05$).

Table 7

Significant Difference in the Level of Management Practices in the Implementation of School Improvement Plan When Grouped According to School Profile

Management Practices	Profile Variables	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Planning	School Size	0.894	not significant	do not reject Ho
	Geographic Location	0.990		
	Title of School Head	0.742		
Implementing	School Size	0.681		
	Geographic Location	0.785		
	Title of School Head	0.681		
Monitoring and Evaluation	School Size	0.878		
	Geographic Location	0.822		
	Title of School Head	0.878		
Adjusting Plans	School Size	0.655		
	Geographic Location	0.778		
	Title of School Head	0.655		

Part IV. Challenges Encountered in the Implementation of Management Practices.

Figure 3 shows the themes generated from the interview with the school heads regarding the challenges they encountered in the implementation of management practices in terms of planning the School Improvement Plan (SIP).

Figure 3
Challenges in Planning School Improvement Plan

Figure 4 shows the themes regarding the challenges the school heads encountered in implementing management practices in terms of the SIP.

Figure 4
Challenges in Implementing a School Improvement Plan

Figure 5 displays the themes regarding the challenges the school heads encountered in monitoring and evaluating the SIP.

Figure 5

Challenges in Monitoring and Evaluation of School Improvement Plan

Figure 6 shows the themes regarding the challenges the school heads encountered in plan adjustment of the SIP.

Figure 6

Challenges in Adjusting Plans of School Improvement Plan

Part V. Coping Strategies Employed by the Respondents to Address the Challenges Encountered

Figure 7 presents the thematic analysis of the coping strategies the school heads employed to address the challenges they encountered in planning the School Improvement Plan (SIP).

Figure 7

Coping Strategies in Planning School Improvement Plan

Figure 8 shows the themes of the coping strategies the school heads employed in implementing the SIP.

Figure 8

Coping Strategies in Implementing of School Improvement Plan

Figure 9 displays the themes of the coping strategies the school heads employed in monitoring and evaluating the SIP.

Figure 9

Coping Strategies in Monitoring and Evaluating the School Improvement Plan

Figure 10 shows the themes of the coping strategies the school heads employed in plan adjustment of the SIP.

Figure 10

Coping Strategies in Adjusting Plans of the School Improvement Plan

Part V. Proposed SIP Management Framework

The following figure shows the proposed SIP management framework.

Figure 11
SIP Management Framework

DISCUSSION

Part I. Profile of the School

Table 2

Profile of the School in Terms of Size, Location, and Title of the School Head

Table 2 shows the school profile of the respondents in terms of the size, location, and title of the school heads. In terms of size, the schools represent an equal population for each school size with a frequency of 4 or 33.33% per category. This is aligned with the DepEd Memorandum No. 47, series 2017, which states that schools shall be categorized as small, medium, large, and mega based on the number of teachers.

Meanwhile, the data for location shows that 4 or 33.33% belong to central schools, while 8 or 66.66% belong to non-central schools. This implies that most of the schools are in metropolitan areas of the town.

In terms of the title of the school heads, there is an equal number of principals, head teachers, and teachers-in-charge.

Part II. Level of Management Practices in the Implementation of School Improvement Plan as Assessed by the School Heads and Teachers

Table 3

Level of Management Practices in the Implementation of School Improvement Plan in Terms of Planning

Table 3 shows the level of management practices in the implementation of School Improvement Plan (SIP) of school heads in terms of planning. The general mean of 3.98 from school heads and 4.0 from teachers reveal that the school heads' management practices in planning are highly practiced. These data indicate a commendably high level of engagement in planning within the context of the SIP. It suggests that, on average, the surveyed administrators are actively and effectively participating in various planning activities to enhance the overall functioning of the school.

Planning is paramount in managing SIPs. It encompasses systematic processes, involves collaborative efforts, and aligns with assessment practices. Effective planning, backed by thorough assessment, sets the stage for strategic initiatives that drive educational institutions toward optimal outcomes. Collaboration among stakeholders and careful consideration of both content and process lenses enhance the efficacy of planning within the context of school improvement. Further, commencement planning empowers educational establishments to define their objectives and aspirations for enhancement with precision. By pinpointing specific benchmarks, schools channel their energies toward targeted domains requiring amelioration, such as academic performance, student engagement, or infrastructural advancement (Smith, 2018).

Table 4

Level of Management Practices in the Implementation of School Improvement Plan in Terms of Implementing

Table 4 presents the level of management practices in implementing of School Improvement Plan (SIP) of school heads in terms of implementing. With an average mean score of 3.92 from school heads and 3.4 from teachers, the level of management practices in terms of implementing is described as "highly practiced". This infers that the administrators demonstrate a solid commitment to effectively implementing the SIP and associated activities for continuous school improvement.

Among the statements, it is notable that statements 1, 3, and 8, respectively, fall within the "moderately practiced". This indicates a proactive approach to involving policies, delivery, and pilot testing in program implementation and adhering to formulated school-based policies, rules, and procedures to enhance the school's continuous growth. Moreover, this means that the administrators are effectively translating planning into practice. This level of management practice underscores the commitment to executing the SIP and engaging stakeholders during the implementation. This dedication lays a strong foundation for actualizing school improvement strategies. Overall, the administrators' engagement demonstrates a robust commitment to implementing the SIP, fostering continuous improvement within the school community.

These findings are in consonance with the study of Jasul (2013), which stated that program implementation is converged to direct and monitor the conduct of various activities. It can be done by providing guidance and directions to work teams in the performance of assigned tasks, ensuring work programs are accomplished as planned, and monitoring actual accomplishments vis-a-vis identified needs and planned activities.

Table 5

Level of Management Practices in the Implementation of School Improvement Plan in Terms of Monitoring and Evaluation

Table 5 displays data on the level of management practices in the implementation of School Improvement Plan (SIP) of school heads in terms of monitoring and evaluation. With an average mean score of 3.94 from the school heads and 3.35 from the teachers, the level of management practices in terms of monitoring and evaluation is categorized as "highly practiced" and "moderately practiced" respectively. This means that administrators demonstrate a solid commitment to effectively monitoring and evaluating the SIP's implementation and outcomes. Moreover, these data underscore administrators' dedication to involving teachers, pupil representatives, school planning teams, and stakeholders in the monitoring and evaluation process, as well as revising programs and projects based on reliable data to improve effectiveness. In addition, these reflect administrators' commitment to providing valuable feedback to the school community, making necessary adjustments to meet targets, and informing stakeholders about the school's status through report cards.

Despite this level of management practice, Statements 1, 2, 4, 8, and 9 show slightly lower mean scores from teachers, which fall under "moderately practiced". These scores indicate administrators' dedication to identifying hindrances, listening to the perspectives of pupils, parents, and stakeholders, and conducting comprehensive reviews to ensure the effectiveness of implemented strategies. This also implies that administrators have a solid commitment to monitoring and evaluating aspects of the SIP.

Although there were differing levels of management practices from school heads and teachers, the data still highlight their dedication to continuously assessing and enhancing the implementation of programs and projects. This commitment establishes a solid foundation for measuring the success of the SIP and ensuring ongoing improvement within the school community.

This aligns with the study of Williams (2021), who argued that monitoring and evaluation catalyze continuous improvement in school management. Their findings indicate that schools that actively monitor and evaluate their improvement plans are more likely to engage in reflective practices, adapt strategies, and foster a culture of learning and accountability.

Table 6

Level of Management Practices in the Implementation of School Improvement Plan in Terms of Adjusting Plans

Table 6 presents data on the level of management practices in the implementation of School Improvement Plan (SIP) of school heads in terms of adjusting plans. With an average mean score of 3.95 from school heads and 3.45 from teachers, the level of management practices in terms of plan adjustment is categorized as "highly practiced". This means that administrators demonstrate a solid commitment to effectively adjusting plans for continuous improvement. This also indicates their proactive approach to assessing existing data to identify priority improvement areas and regularly checking the progress of school programs, projects, and activities for effective plan adjustments. These data reflect administrators' consistent commitment to identifying the root causes of problems through listening to learners' perspectives, incorporating existing data into crafting adjusted annual implementation plans, using collected data to formulate new programs, and making necessary adjustments to strategies and techniques.

Moreover, the findings suggest that administrators are dedicated to the process of plan adjustments within the SIP framework. The "highly practiced" category across the statements underscore their commitment to continuously improving and adapting plans based on data and stakeholder input. This proactive approach establishes a solid foundation for flexibility and responsiveness within the school's improvement initiatives, ultimately contributing to a more effective and dynamic school environment.

Part III. Level of Management Practices in the Implementation of School Improvement Plan When Grouped According to School Profile

The following statistical table shows a significant difference in the level of management practices in the SIP of school heads when grouped according to profile.

Table 7

Significant Difference in the Level of Management Practices in the Implementation of School Improvement Plan When Grouped According to School Profile

Table 7 shows that the difference in the level of management practices in the implementation of School Improvement Plan when the respondents are grouped into profiles is not statistically significant ($p = .894, .990, .742, .681, .785, .681, .878, .878, .822, .878,$

.655, .778, .655 > .05). These findings illustrate that the respondents' responses do not differ when grouped according to school size, geographic location, and title of the school head.

School heads are mandated by policies and memoranda, which they follow from the top management down to the schools and school managers. Republic Act 9155 established the School Improvement Plan (SIP) as an integral part of the DepEd's School-Based Management approach. SIP is a strategic roadmap for educational change, focusing on improving student achievement through curriculum enhancement, positive learning environments, and increased parental involvement. SIP follows three phases—Assess, Plan, and Act—and involves collaboration among school personnel, the community, and stakeholders. Implementing SIP practices has been shown to contribute significantly to better student and school performance.

The effective execution of a School Improvement Plan (SIP) holds considerable significance for the success of educational institutions, with the implementation process playing a vital role in influencing the level of management practice within SIP management. Implementation involves translating the plan's goals into actionable steps, and its efficacy directly affects the achievement of intended outcomes and overall school performance. Effective leadership, resource availability, collaboration among stakeholders, and communication channels influence successful implementation. The alignment of management practices with the SIP's strategies, evidenced-based decision-making, progress monitoring, feedback provision, and adaptive adjustments contribute to refined management practices. This, in turn, enhances student achievement and school standing, creating a symbiotic relationship between successful implementation and improved management practices (Spillane et al., 2004)

Part IV. Challenges Encountered in the Implementation of Management Practices.

Figure 3

Challenges in Planning School Improvement Plan

Theme 1. Conflict of Time

Based on the interview with the school heads, they all claimed that one of the challenges they face is conflict of time. This is because of the different school programs and activities held in their school.

Theme 2. Unclear Goals

The school heads also admitted that identifying or measuring goals is the top most challenge. This is because they see rising challenges in SIP.

Theme 3. Lack of Training

The school heads also admitted during the interview that lack of training for teachers and other stakeholders is one of the challenges they experience.

This implies that most school heads consider involving people, the community, and stakeholders to be their main challenge. Planning with difficulty in involvement may lead to problems in crafting a good SIP.

Dabesa et al (2021) the studied on the SIP and some of the cited challenges were the there is a shortage of financial support, lack of awareness and lack of training among stakeholders. The results also indicate that there is lack of learning facilities and poor community participation. The study revealed poor management, poor community mobilization, and poor collaboration in SIP implementation.

Figure 4

Challenges in Implementing a School Improvement Plan

Theme 1. Lack of Coordination

Most of the school heads admitted that one of the challenges they encounter in implementing SIP is the lack of coordination among teachers. It is clear that most of them have the same level of agreement on how they encounter coordination as difficult to the internal and external partners since they need to tap different agencies.

Theme 2. Lack of Resources

Another challenge that they encounter is the lack of resources and overlapping of activities in school. This is because of the different programs that need to be administered. Meanwhile, they believe that overlapping reports also hinder their ability to outsource and have more efficient time.

This is aligned with the challenges in the implementing the SIP. Coburn and Penuel (2016), claimed to accentuate the pivotal role of robust collaborative cultures and effective communication channels in nurturing successful implementation. Effective implementation necessitates aligning management practices with the goals and strategies enshrined in the SIP. Lack of coordination with the stakeholders and problems on resources affects the SIP implementation. However different activities or overlapping of Activities could also affect the implementing activities, programs and projects in SIP.

Figure 5

Challenges in Monitoring and Evaluation of School Improvement Plan

Theme 1. Unavailability for Meetings and Feedback

According to the interview, most school heads acknowledged that their biggest difficulty in monitoring and evaluating SIP is gathering feedback from stakeholders through meetings. This implies that getting together with internal and external partners to get their input and program results could be challenging or may take a longer period.

Theme 2. No Data Collected

Gathering and processing data also presented difficulties for a few of the school administrators. For some of the school heads, gathering the data required for reporting and documentation presented additional difficulties. Compiling all the necessary information might have taken a while.

In terms of monitoring and evaluation Blackstein (2020) several factors can affect its effectiveness but M& E is highly influence by unavailability for meetings and feedback among the stakeholders. Lack of meetings and feedback during the M&E leads to no data collection for evaluation.

Figure 6

Challenges in Adjusting Plans of School Improvement Plan.

Theme 1. Limited Funds and Resources

Most of the school heads claimed that there were limited funds and resources to implement the adjusted plan. Aspects of SIP is resource generation. Most school heads struggle to decide where to get funds for the activities and programs. Because of targeted plans and programs, some other factors might not have been possible to anticipate during the planning. This may lead to challenges and difficulties that need plans and adjustments.

Theme 2. Limited Time to Go Over

Another challenge that most of the school heads mentioned was the limited time to go over the adjusted plan. This suggests that school heads may fail to consider certain demands while planning, resulting in plans and modifications that are crucial components of SIP.

Agra (2023) the Department of Education may provide training to school personnel as well as representatives from its stakeholders for effective adjusting of plans the SIP in all schools may form a school improvement committee, which will begin the process of developing a school improvement plan in which the major challenges are the availability of resources or limited resources and school heads limited time to go over and create strategies to attract stakeholders to extend appropriate financial support and generate income-generating projects to finance the school projects and programs, and all schools may encourage practical involvement of all stakeholders by raising awareness of the importance of SIP implementation.

Part V. Coping Strategies Employed by the Respondents to Address the Challenges Encountered

Figure 7

Coping Strategies in Planning School Improvement Plan

Theme 1. Conduct Vision Sharing

To cope up with the challenges encountered in planning SIP, most school heads conduct vision sharing with the stakeholders.

Theme 2. Conduct of Programs for the Improvement of SIP

Some of the school heads also claimed that they conduct programs for the improvement of SIP.

Theme 3. Organize SIP Committee

Some of the school heads also organize SIP committee to cope up with the challenges in the planning stage.

Theme 4. Allow Everyone to Participate

Some of the school heads believed that letting them be part of the programs and committee would help them cope also with the challenges.

Brown and Johnson (2020) claimed that implementing effective management practices within school improvement plans is crucial for achieving successful educational outcomes. As various studies have demonstrated, leadership qualities like vision sharing, conduct different programs for SIP and communication skills significantly impact the execution of improvement plans

Figure 8

Coping Strategies in the Implementation of School Improvement Plan

Theme 1. Ensure Quality, Efficiency, and Timeliness

The school heads believe that their coping strategies mainly ensure the quality, efficiency, and timeliness of the implementation of SIP.

Theme 2. Dissemination of the Student's Performance

Based on the interview, some of the school heads claimed that the dissemination of students' performance is essential.

Theme 3. Increase the Extent of the Involvement

During the interview, one school head claimed that increasing the extent of involvement is their way of coping.

The school head, alongside the project team, crafts an annual implementation plan derived from the SIP. This plan outlines strategies, learning activities, time frames,

responsible individuals, and resources needed to achieve set objectives for the school year (Luistro, 2015).

Figure 9

Coping Strategies in Monitoring and Evaluating the School Improvement Plan

Theme 1. Create Tools

The school heads were able to create tools to help with the programs and activities to cope with the needs and challenges in the SIP.

Theme 2. Consult with the Team

The school heads believe that they should conduct a consultation with the team.

Theme 3. Consider Suggestions

Some of the school heads consider suggestions.

In Monitoring and Evaluation Brown (2018) emphasized that in monitoring and evaluation it is a must to create tools that would help greatly the monitoring of SIP. They also need to consult with the team every time they needed and lastly all the suggestions of the members must consider.

Figure 10

Coping Strategies in Adjusting Plans of the School Improvement Plan

Theme 1. Develop Plan and Activities

For plan adjustment, the school heads mentioned that they try to cope with the challenges by developing plans and activities.

Theme 2. Attend Postgraduate and Attend Seminars

Meanwhile, some school heads claimed that they attend postgraduate and seminars to cope with the plan adjustments in SIP.

Theme 3. Solicit by Tapping

School heads admitted that some of them solicit ideas from stakeholders. Plans and adjustments are necessary for the implementation. These involve translating the plan's goals into actionable steps. Their efficacy directly affects the achievement of intended outcomes and overall school performance. Effective leadership, resource availability, collaboration among stakeholders, and communication channels influence successful implementation.

Adjusting plans according to Vangronigen (2023) emphasized that SIP focused more on developing SIPs plan and activities, SIP team should attend seminar to raising concerns about SIPs continuing to be enacted out of compliance by soliciting by tapping to the

stakeholders rather than as a mechanism for spurring and sustaining improvement efforts in schools

Part V. Proposed SIP Management Framework

The results presented in the previous parts serve as input for developing the SIP Management Framework. The framework deals with four areas: planning, implementing, monitoring and evaluation, and adjusting plans. The management framework will guide school heads, the school planning team, and teachers in developing SIPs for planning, implementing, monitoring, evaluating, and adjusting school activities for the whole school year. It is also intended to resolve issues or challenges encountered during the project's planning, implementation, monitoring, evaluation, and plan adjustment phases.

Summary of Findings

This part presents the summary of findings which provides a gist of the significant results of the study.

1. On the Profile of the School

1.1 In terms of School Size, the school represents an equal population for each school size with a frequency of 4 or 33.33% per category.

1.2 In terms of Geographic Location, it shows that 4 or 33.33% belong to central schools, while 8 or 66.66% belong to non-central schools. This implies that most of the school are in urban areas of the town.

1.3 In terms of Title of the School Head, there is an equal number of principals, head teachers and teachers-in-charge with a frequency of 4 or 33.33%.

2. On the Level of management practices of School Heads in the implementation of School Improvement Plan as assessed by the teachers and the school heads.

2.1 The findings showed that the level of management practices in the implementation of School Improvement Plan of school heads in terms planning was 3.98 from school heads and 4.0 from teachers reveal that the school head's management practices are highly practiced. These data indicate a commendably high level of engagement in planning.

2.2 As to level of management practices in the implementation of school improvement plan of school heads in terms of implementing is describe as highly practiced with an average mean score of 3.92 from school heads and 3.4 from teachers. This infers that administrators demonstrated a solid commitment to effectively implementing the SIP.

2.3 With regards to the level of management practices in the implementation of School Improvement Plan of school heads the monitoring and evaluation is categorized as highly practiced with an average mean score of 3.94 from the school heads and moderately practiced from the teachers with 3.35 with an average mean score. The administrators demonstrate a solid commitment to effectively monitors and evaluates the SIP's implementation and outcomes.

2.4 Concerning the level of management practices in the implementation of School Improvement Plan of school heads in adjusting plans the average mean scores of 3.95 from school heads and 3.45 from teachers it is categorized as highly practiced that administrators demonstrate solid commitment into effectively adjusting plans.

3. On the Level of Management practices of School Heads in the Implementation of School Improvement Plan as assessed by the teachers and the school heads.

The significant difference in the level of management practices in the implementation of SIP of school heads when grouped according to school profile is not statistically significant. The respondents' responses do not differ when grouped according to school size, geographic location, and title of the school heads variables.

4. On the challenges encountered by the school heads in the Implementation of Management Practices

The challenges encountered in the implementation of management practices were gathering persons involved in planning due to conflict of time, coordinating with the internal and external stakeholders to create a plan for priority of improvement, meeting with the stakeholders to collect feedback, and limited funds and resources to implement the adjusted plan.

5. On the coping strategies employed by the school heads to address Challenges Encountered

Teachers and School heads coping strategies to address the challenges encountered included conducting vision sharing with the stakeholders, ensuring quality, efficiency, and timeliness, creating localized monitoring and evaluation tools, and solving difficulties in the plan and adjustments. They claimed that they develop plans and activities to attract stakeholders.

6. A SIP Management Framework was proposed based on the findings of the study that is intended to resolve issues or challenges encountered during the project's planning, implementing, monitoring, evaluation, and adjusting plans phases.

Conclusions

1. The school profile of the respondents in terms of school size and title of the school heads are the same while in geographic location most of the respondents came from non-central schools.

2. The level of management practices of school heads in the implementation of School Improvement Plan assessed by the teachers and school heads in the congressional district in phases of planning, implementing, monitoring and evaluation; and adjusting plans was distinctively to have a high level of practice.
 3. There is no significant difference in the level of management practices in the implementation of SIP of school heads when grouped according to school profile, thus the hypothesis is accepted.
 4. However, challenges occur due to conflict of time, coordinating then collect feedback, and limited funds and resources.
 5. On the other hand, the way of coping strategies is to have quality, efficiency, and timeliness, creating localized monitoring and evaluation tools, and solving difficulties in the plan and adjustments.
 6. A SIP Management Framework that was made based from the results can be applied for school heads challenges in management practices.
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Recommendations

Based on the conclusions drawn, the following are recommended:

1. Since then, the profile of the schools is coming from non-central schools with head teachers leading the schools. The head teacher may continue to intensify collaborations with stakeholders on their needs and weaknesses to improve their current skills.
2. The implementation of School Improvement Plan (SIP) management practices of school heads are highly practiced. They may intensively help the teachers and students through consistent communication and provide training designs that will further improve the school.
3. Continuous coordination of schools and school stakeholders must be practiced for the improvement of the SIP implementation.
4. School heads may create a learning atmosphere conducive to building a collaborative environment and setting shared goals to achieve a comprehensive and inclusive approach to instruction. School heads may prioritize monitoring and evaluation as components of technical assistance practices. Through monitoring tools, school heads can utilize regular observations, documented progress, and timely teacher feedback.
5. Future researchers may conduct further research and investigation to pinpoint strategies to enhance practices related to consistent technical assistance/staffing scheduling, creating a hospitable setting for teachers and students, designing activities that encourage project flow, and planning training for teacher development.
6. Other schools can apply, use, and benchmark a SIP management framework plan to improve the implementation of the SIP.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study applied ethical consideration primarily to protect the respondents. To adhere to promote the aims of the research imparting authentic knowledge, truth and prevention of error. Furthermore, following ethics enables to deal collaborative approach towards the study with the assistance of their peers, mentors and other contributors to the study (Chetty, 2016). The researcher assures to protect the respondents by maintaining kept the identity of the respondents and use only the data for the data gathering only.

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